

Style of Painter Rajesh Saggi: A Look at His Work

Rajesh Saggi is [a painter who has been creating a stir in the art world](#) for the past several years. Though he may not have achieved recognition as an artist, his work has been consistently praised for its artistic merit and its ability to communicate ideas through its subject matter. In fact, one of the best things about his paintings is that you don't have to understand or agree with their message in order to enjoy them. You can just look at them and see for yourself that they are beautiful paintings with great attention to detail, colours that pop, and imagery that makes sense.

Rajesh Saggi's Style?

So, we've already discussed what makes Rajesh Saggi's work different from other painters. Now, let's get into how he does it. Saggi's painting style is referred to as Cubism-inspired Modernism. It's a style that has a very distinct and original approach to painting, which we'll discuss below. If you're not familiar with the term Modernism, it's an art movement that originated in France during the 1880s. It was inspired by the modern and scientific movements of the time and sought to combine these movements with the traditions of art and architecture of the Middle Ages, Renaissance, and ancient Greece in order to create a new hybrid style. Descriptions of his work include "a sense of balance that is almost optical, a colour that is both warm and cool at the same time, and a sense

of space and light that are both simple and complex at the same time”.

The Language of Rajesh Saggi Paintings:

Like many great writers and artists, Rajesh Saggi’s art is all about communicating ideas with imagery. In his paintings, you’ll frequently see bright and bold colours, strong lines, and a lot of contrasts. Rajesh Saggi’s [artistic style](#) is often described as “Vedic”, which refers to his use of bright and bold colors that remind you of nature. Sometimes, his works explore serious subjects such as war, religion, and human relationships, while other times, he focuses more on social issues such as poverty, pollution, and war. You’ll notice that many of his paintings have symbols such as clouds, trees, and animals in them. These symbols refer to different things such as morality, spirituality, and human relationships.

Difference between Indian and Western Art Forms in Rajesh Saggi's Work:

As you might’ve gathered by now, [Rajesh Saggi](#) is an artist who loves to draw inspiration from nature. This is evident in his work in many ways, including in his use of vibrant and exotic colours. However, he also creates works that draw inspiration from other forms of art, such as the architecture and decorative arts of other cultures. You’ll occasionally see works that draw inspiration from architecture and other decorative arts of other cultures such as India’s Taj Mahal.